
Quality Assurance Plan

Deliverable D1.3

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Executive summary

The present document summarizes the internal procedures outlined for ensuring the high level of quality work proposed within the nodes of the BETTER4U project, thus completing the information stated in the project's Grant and Consortium Agreements (GA & CA). Therefore, the objective of the present document is to set forth the techniques that will be used to provide adequate resources and measures to ensure satisfactory outcomes of high quality.

Disclaimer

The present document does not in any way overrule the Grant Agreement (incl. Annexes associated) and the Consortium Agreement.

Document information

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Statement of Originality

Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CMT	Coordination and Management Team
CO	Coordinator
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
FSIGN	Financial Signatory
GA	Grant Agreement or General Assembl
PO	Project Officer
SC	Steering Committee
WP(s)	Work Package (s)

1. Introduction

D1.3 Quality assurance plan aims at presenting the cornerstones set at ensuring: i) the quality of work carried out and produced within the BETTER4U activities, and ii) the smooth cooperation and conduct between partners and work packages (WPs). The present document will, thus, outline: i) the tools and platforms used to manage the interactions between partners throughout their involvement in the project activities and check the progress of project works, ii) the ways of documentation exchange between project partners, as well as between project partners and the European Commission, and; iii) the standards of editorial content for the project documents (definitions of templates and policies used for the documentation, presentation and communication).

Complementary to the present plan, the BETTER4U project will be conducted based on the cornerstone reference documents, i.e. the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreements (GA & CA), the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan prepared by WP9 leader European Food Information Council (EUFIC), as well as the reference documents available by the European Commission.

2. Documentation

2.1. Management of Documents and Records

The BETTER4U consortium uses two online platforms for document communication and record keeping. The project's coordination and management team (CMT) has created and shared with all consortium partners i) a shared folder using the "Google Drive" platform (the [BETTER4U shared Google Drive folder](#) and ii) a page on the "Pumble" platform" to facilitate rapid exchanges and record keeping of key-consortium documents such as the contact list (the [BETTER4U Pumble page](#)). Both platforms can be used to upload files and share files. Google Drive can additionally be used to organize files and create sub-files as well as use files offline. Documents and files shared via Pumble can be uploaded in the "[Files](#)" section and /or pinned under the "[#General](#)" channel. Use of those widely shared repositories eliminates barriers related to functionality and increases the smooth and safe document exchange by decreasing the number of email attachments.

Access to both has been granted only to consortium members who are involved in the works of the project upon approval by the CMT. In case a consortium member cannot access the shared files using their institutional email, they should inform the CMT. Access to personal emails instead will only take place after approval by the CO. Any member no longer involved in the project should inform the CMT in timely manner, who will subsequently remove all access rights from their corresponding emails.

2.2. Deliverables and Templates

The BETTER4U project is organized in such a way so that each activity conducted leads to the creation of outputs produced in the form of deliverables. The latter will be produced as either of the two types of “Document, report” or “Other”. The former refer to all document deliverables based on a common project template provided by WP9 leader, EUFIC, while the latter correspond to all other outputs. In the “Other” category, BETTER4U deliverables will concern the Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based causal model and the BETTER4U mobile application. In those cases, the deliverables will include the software and the technical reports explaining the design and the functionalities of the outputs delivered.

Deliverable creation and submission to the European Commission (EC) for consideration and approval will take place as described in the project’s Description of Action (DoA). All deliverables are subject to acceptance by the consortium and GA and will be provided to the project coordinator (CO) who is responsible for review and submission to the EC.

2.3. Quality Assurance

Assuring the quality of the produced outputs is a key priority in BETTER4U activities. Quality assurance of the produced deliverables is promoted by: i) use of the shared templates including predefined formatting and structure rules, as provided by WP9 leader, EUFIC (available at the BETTER4U Google Drive shared folder, under [the BETTER4U Templates sub-folder](#)); ii) review performed by the CO and consortium members involved in the corresponding deliverable; and iii) final review by the CMT prior to submission to the EC. The objectives of those measures are to i) produce appropriate and adequate deliverables in a timely manner, and ii) identify potential risks and corresponding mitigation actions in a proactive way.

Deliverable quality will be evaluated based on: i) appropriateness, i.e. whether the deliverable is fit-for-purpose, indeed describes the output it was firstly designed for and focuses on the goals; ii) readability, i.e. ensuring the deliverable has appropriate length, corresponding references wherever applicable and is free from spelling and language errors; iii) completeness, i.e. ensuring the deliverable address its objectives, the goals described are Specific, Measurable, Appropriate, Realistic and Timely (SMART) and contains all appropriate sections and chapters; and iv) consistency, i.e. ensuring cohesion and coherence among all chapters, as well as accordance with the deliverables of the WPs.

In the case of expected delays in the drafting or delivery process, the authors must report back to the WP leader and CO describing the causes of the delay and inform of an approximate late-delivery date. In the case of significant delays, the CO is responsible for informing the Project Officer (PO). As an additional way to assure and manage the progress, quality and the timely execution of the works proposed within the project, three bodies have been created consisting of consortium partners, namely: i) the Task Force for data Analysis, chaired by the University of Tartu; ii) the Task Force for the Development of Novel Models and Tools, headed by Aristotle University of Thessaloniki; and iii) an Interdisciplinary Knowledge Group (IKG),

headed by Harokopio University of Athens. Each body is headed by a partner for the duration of the project and body members have been proposed by each partner and approved by the GA (see **Tables 1-3** for the members of each body).

Table 1. Members of the Task Force for Data Analysis

No	Organization	Organization Abbreviation	Member(s)
1	HAROKOPIO PANEPISTIMIO	HUA	Panagiotis Moulos, Christos Diou, Ioanna Panagiota Kalafati, Maria Kafyra
2	HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO	UH	Karri Silventoinen, Jaacko Kaprio
3	UNIwersytet SWPS	SWPS	Aleksandra Łuszczńska
4	TARTU ULIKOOL	UTARTU	Anders Eriksson (<i>Leader</i>)
5	HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM MUENCHEN	HMGU	Elisabeth Thiering
6	STICHTING VU	VUA	Dorret I. Boomsma, Rene Pool
7	WEIZMANN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE	WIS	Eran Segal, David Krongauz
8	WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES S.A.	WINGS	Vera Stavroulaki
9	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Anastasios Delopoulos
10	UNIVERSITAET BERN	UBern	Stavroula Mouggiakakou
11	BRADFORD TEACHING HOSPITALS NHS FOUNDATION TRUST	BiB	Gillian Santorelli
12	QUEEN MARY UNIVERSITY OF LONDON	QMUL	Eirini Marouli

Table 2. Members of the Task Force for the Development of Novel Models and Tools

No	Organization	Organization Abbreviation	Member(s)
1	CHAROKOPIO PANEPISTIMIO	HUA	Christos Diou
2	WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES S.A.	WINGS	Vera Stavroulaki
3	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Anastasios Delopoulos (<i>Leader</i>)
4	UNIVERSITAET BERN	UBern	Stavroula Mouggiakakou

Table 3. Members of the Interdisciplinary Knowledge Group (IKG)

No	Organization	Organization Abbreviation	Member
1	CHAROKOPIO PANEPISTIMIO	HUA	George Dedoussis, Yannis Manios, Christos Diou, Panagiotis Moulos, Ioanna Panagiota Kalafati, Maria Kafyra, Eva Karaglani (<i>Leader</i>)

2	CENTRO DE ESTUDOS E INVESTIGAÇÃO EM DINÂMICAS SOCIAIS E SAÚDE	CEIDSS	Ana Rito
3	CENTRE DE RECHERCHE EN NUTRITION HUMAINE RHONE-ALPES	CRNH-RA	Julie-Anne Nazarre, Anestis Dougkas
4	REGION HOVEDSTADEN	REGIONH	Klaus Bønnelykke
5	EUROPEAN FOOD INFORMATION COUNCIL	EUFIC	Stephan Kampshoff
6	DIETHNES PANEPISTIMIO ELLADOS	IHU	Maria Hassapidou, Ion Pagkalos
7	Karolinska Institutet	KI	Ioannis Ioakeimidis
8	MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	MUW	Eva Schernhammer
9	UNIVERSITY OF CYPRUS	UCY	Constantinos Deltas
10	HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO	UH	Karri Silventoinen, Jaacko Kaprio
11	UNIVERSIDAD DE NAVARRA	UNAV	Maira Bes Rastrollo
12	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	UGent	Nick Verhaeghe, Ruben Willems
13	UNIWERSYTET SWPS	SWPS	Aleksandra Łuszczzyńska
14	TARTU ULIKOOL	UTARTU	Anders Eriksson
15	HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM MUENCHEN	HMGU	Elisabeth Thiering
16	STICHTING VU	VUA	Dorret I. Boomsma, Rene Pool
17	THE EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE STUDY OF OBESITY	EASO	Lisa Heggie
18	UNIVERSITAT WIEN	UNIVIE	Lisa Marie Breyer, Rodessa May Marquez
19	WEIZMANN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE	WIS	Eran Segal, David Krongauz
20	WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES S.A.	WINGS	Vera Stavroulaki
21	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI CAGLIARI	UNICA	Vasilios Fanos
22	BIOCLINICA SA	BIOCLINICA SA	Cristinel Gheorghiu
23	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Anastasios Delopoulos
24	TAMPERE UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL AND TAMPERE UNIVERSITY	TAUH	Terho Lehtimäki
25	UNIVERSITAET BERN	UBern	Stavroula Mougiakakou
26	QIMR Berghofer Medical Research Institute	QIMR	Nick Martin
27	BRADFORD TEACHING HOSPITALS NHS FOUNDATION TRUST	BiB	Gillian Santorelli
28	QUEEN MARY UNIVERSITY OF LONDON	QMUL	Eirini Marouli

Those three bodies have been created by the consortium members as an additional measure of quality assurance and promotion of the appropriate and timely conduct of WP activities. As shown in **Figure 1**, the Task Force for Data Analysis concerns the activities of WPs 3 to 7, mainly focusing on the handling of retrospective and prospective data of the BETTER4U dataset. The Task Force for the Development of Novel Models and Tools primarily refers to WPs 5 & 6, where the AI-based model, the BETTER4U platform and the BETTER4U mobile application will be developed. Finally, the IKG has been created to support the activities of both Task Forces by providing managing and healthcare professionals’ knowledge required which might potentially not be related to technical or technological matters.

Figure 1. BETTER4U Task Forces and Interdisciplinary Knowledge Group

2.4. Planning and Reporting

Within the BETTER4U nodes, the CMT is responsible for planning tasks aiming at: i) tracking the overall progress of the project; ii) promoting the high-quality reporting of the produced outputs; iii) proactively detecting potential risks in timely manner to allow for contingency actions to take place as soon as possible. The overall supervision of the project activities is a work of the Steering Committee (SC), consisting of all nine WP leaders. The CO and the CMT are continuously involved in all SC activities and planning. WP leaders are, in turn, responsible for planning the tasks involved in their corresponding WP, assisted by the CO and the CMT wherever required. The CMT is responsible for monitoring the progress of all works conducted within the project’s nodes and the appropriateness and eligibility of all costs reported. In this context, the CMT has created a BETTER4U Google calendar, inserting all important timeframes and deadlines to track the timeframe of project progress, ensure the timely communication of all partners on project matters, as well as the delivery of all project outputs. Project dissemination and communication activities are reported by each partner and tracked down by WP9 Leader, EUFIC, via use of a communication tracking sheet. All partners are

informed of project meetings as per the CA and in-person meetings are communicated to the consortium within a minimum of three months prior to the conduct of the meeting.

Project activities are tracked down by periodic reporting via the deliverables, milestones, outcomes, risks and indicators throughout the project lifecycle. Periodic reports will be further submitted to the EC by the CO within 60 days following the end of each reporting period. For BETTER4U, three periodic reports are scheduled at the end of the 18, 36 and 48-month periods after project onset (i.e. in April 2025, October 2026 and October 2027, respectively). Periodic reports are two-fold, comprising of a technical and a financial report. The former consists of two parts: i) part A, which is submitted by the CO, generated by the IT system and includes the information inserted by the partners on the reporting modules in the Participant Portal, and ii) part B, which is a descriptive part presenting the work conducted during the corresponding reporting period. For the latter, WP and task leaders create a report on their WP tasks and submit it to the CO for review who then submits it to the SC for final approval prior to uploading it to the Participant Portal. The periodic financial report includes: i) a financial statement for each consortium partner detailing all eligible costs made on their part, as well as by any entities affiliated to them, during the reporting period; ii) a statement detailing the use of the resources and any information of potential subcontracting and/or in-kind contributions by third parties; and iii) a “periodic summary financial statement” generated by the IT system including the financial statements from all partners signed by their Financial Signatory (FSIGN) and submitted to the EC by the CO.

Finally, a final report must be submitted to the EC by the CO, within 60 calendar days after the end of the last reporting period (i.e. until January December 30th 2027 for the BETTER4U project). Similarly to the aforementioned, the final report must include a final technical and a final financial report. The former shall include the entirety of project results, their dissemination and communication actions, the conclusions and the overall impact of the project. The latter shall include the “final summary financial statement” consisting of all financial statements for all partners throughout the three reporting periods and the “certificate on the financial statements” for each partners in case a total reimbursement of more than EUR 325 000 of actual direct and unit costs is requested.

3. Communication

3.1. Communication tools

All modern communication tools have been put in place for use in the project, as to effectively facilitate communications and project output. Communication tools include e-mail, mail, use of the Pumble platform, phone and video conferences, as described in **Table 4**.

Table 4. BETTER4U communication tools

Communication Tools	Purpose	Access/ Conditions
E-mail	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussions and updates on project matters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not to be used in the exchange of large files, data or other sensitive project material
Mail	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exchange of original documents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By secure mail in the case of confidential material
Pumble	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussions and updates on project matters Rapid communications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inclusion by invite sent to partner member by the CMT By login using personal passwords
Phone	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussions and updates on project matters Rapid communications Confirmation of important decisions made in writing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of professional telephone number lines Minimization of use of personal telephone lines
Video Conference (VC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular and urgent meetings of governance bodies and Task Forces Short meetings for discussions and updates on project matters. Increase in effectiveness, communication and decrease in travel costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inclusion by invite sent to the partner member by the call organizer Timely distribution of meeting agendas prior to the meeting and/or according to the CA, if applicable (i.e. meetings of governance bodies) Timely distribution of meeting minutes after meeting conclusion or according to the CA, if applicable (i.e. meetings of governance bodies)

3.2. Consortium contact list

In order to facilitate communications and effective exchanges, the project's coordination and management team (CMT) have created a listed excel file including all consortium partner contact details, available at the project's both [BETTER4U shared Google Drive folder](#) (under sub-folder "[BETTER4U Consortium Details](#)") and the [BETTER4U Pumble page](#) (pinned under the "[#General](#)" channel). The list includes an overview of the members included in the project's governance bodies and task forces, as well as details on the persons to be contacted regarding administrative or communication activities. The list is dynamically updated based on ongoing new additions or potential de-subscriptions to ensure the smooth communication of all project partners and the seamless integration of new members. Only the CMT can edit the contact list.

3.3. E-mails and mailing lists

Emails will remain the main communication means throughout project duration, being complemented by immediate ("chat") exchanges between persons in the project's Pumble page, thus, eliminating any difficulties attributed to geographical and distance parameters. To further enable rapid and effective communications, the WINGS ICT Solutions partner has created a mailing list including the addresses of all project partners. To request inclusion or deletion in or from the mailing list, the persons interested can and will send an e-mail to the CMT who will then contact the WINGS ICT Solutions member managing the mailing list requesting for addition or deletion. The member should state their name, e-mail address and affiliated institution. Only the CMT and the WINGS ICT Solutions member managing the mailing list can edit the mailing list.

The project's CMT will communicate all relevant project information via email and Pumblebot direct communications. File attachment exceeding file size proposed limits will be avoided to ensure the smooth reception of all documents by all partners irrespective of potential restrictions concerning input, file formats or software versions. Such files will be shared and uploaded on the project's [BETTER4U shared Google Drive folder](#) repository, as well as pin them on the [BETTER4U Pumble page](#) (under the "[#General](#)" channel).

To further facilitate partner communication, the CMT has created separate Pumble channels per governance body, WP and Task Force each one including the corresponding partner members as previously agreed by the consortium during its first General Assembly (GA) meeting. The relevance of those channels for each partner primarily stems from the activities as planned in the project's DoA, i.e. If a partner is involved in a task from a specific WP or within the duties of a Task Force, the corresponding WP or Task Force channel will automatically become relevant for that partner. If necessary, corresponding email lists per WP and/or Task Force will be created by the CMT in coordination with the relevant WP Leaders. A separate email address to be used by partners in case of issues arising on ethical or legal matters has been created by WP2 Leader University of Vienna, at BETTER4U-helpdesk.id@univie.ac.at.

4. Conclusion

The outlined approaches for the quality assurance of documentation, planning and communication within the BETTER4U nodes, aim to maximize the quality of the produced outputs and allow for the successful conduct of all scheduled activities. All partners, bodies and the project CO will collaborate in applying and abiding by the aforementioned throughout the duration of the project.

5. Contact and details

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